

WEB APPLICATIONS AND THEIR SOFTWARE

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Abstract: This article provides an overview of web applications and their software. This concept includes the skills and techniques used to create web applications, how they are launched, modified and added to, as well as their presentation to users, data storage and usage features, and many other important issues. The article explains the skills for building web applications and reviews their structure, databases, user interface, software, testing, and features. This article also provides information about web application development and many other important processes. The article also provides an understanding of web application software. This involves running, modifying and adding applications, features, and making them available to users after they are built. The article also provides information about the necessary tools and techniques for software implementation. The article provides an overview of web applications and their software, and provides information on the guides and tools used to create and develop them.

Keywords: web-technologies, Plug-in programs, Web pages, Web pages, XHTML, XML, HTML.

The Internet is bringing different people together with a common goal. Everyone tries to get some kind of information from the Internet. So times it comes the document on the Internet print reach qualification writing use the car each like even to secondary education had of a person from the hand will come.

This article covers creating web documents, publishing them on the Internet, web- the document beautification, interesting and attractive by doing Create, time if it comes whether data update such as tasks to teach intended.

This guide covers creating web documents, publishing them on the Internet, web- make the document more attractive, interesting and attractive, when the time comes whether data update such as tasks to teach intended.

Early web pages had a very simple structure and text formatting and from hyperindicators content found was Web technologies development As a result, Plug-in programs started to be placed in Web pages, as a result Web pages have been given an interactive feature. The development of web technologies one of the final results is script languages (Script Languages). From using them The goal is to facilitate the work of the Web server, a Web server for various tasks bother without such issues user of the computer in itself is to create. One of the latest advances in Web technology is the dynamic Web are pages. Dynamic Web pages are directly related to CGI programs, CGI applications are programs that reside on the server and use the server's capabilities. They are processes incoming requests to the server and, as a result of processing, creates a new Web page harvest will be

Computers to the network connect ideas the first being 1960s in their heads appear be started 1965 year Lawrence Roberts and Thomas Merrville California and Massachusetts in the states is located two the computer to each other connected. The connection was made through telephone lines, the first in the history of the world computer network it has been. This technology with USA Defense Ministry DARPA agency interested in to them military troops one to the network combine idea turn on left Agency specialists this the idea according to hard affairs takego and in 1969 ARPANET network created.

In October 1971, for the first time in the history of mankind, he became an employee of the BBN company Ray Tomlinson sent an email. Text at the top of the keyboard in the line QWERTYUIOP from the letters consists of being Tomlinson's to himselfsent In March 1972 Tomlinson SNGMSG and READMAIL electronic created messaging and reading programs. At the same time, the ARPANET of all to its users sent in the letter electron of addresses @ using the basics of structure declared (login_name@host_name).

in 1974 network development in history TCP/IP (transmission control protocol/internet protocol) as a result of the generation of inter-network protocol rising happen it has been. This of discovery authors Robert Kan and Stanford professor of the university Winton Surf.

At this time, TCP/IP is the protocol for dividing information into packets started This is the protocol now too main protocol used as is coming

Before this discovery, information on the network was transmitted only in text form was Berners-Lee and his colleagues WWW name with famous technologycreated. This technology colorful web pages to create road open the ability to link to other pages on the Internet using hyperlinkscreated in 1993 Mark Andrisen (Marc Andreessen) Illinois state at the university Mosaic named web pages to see created the program.

In 1995, the United States supported the Internet for several years coming. The National Science Foundation has halted its financial spending and beyond The Internet is independent being dependent on no one without being left

web page, website, Web server

- Web technology
- Website
- Web server
- Web page

A web page is a special browser that has its own unique address using (browser) visible is a document. To him text, graphics, sound, video or animation data union - multimedia documents, another to documents hyperlinks entrance possible

Website - one how much of web pages makes sense union.

Web server - to the network connected computer or in it program considered provides common resources to the client or performs tasks of managing them. Internet network to users network resources free use opportunity giving web without servers imagination reached won't be. Such on servers on the Internet present of the information provided big part aggregated.

Internet of the network work principle TCP/IP (Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol - data transfer protocol/Internet protocol) computer in the network information transmission records of the set is the name.

TCP (Transmission Control protocol). Acceptance doer and transmitter support computer communication based on logical connections - charging account.

IP (Internet protocol)- Information transmission provides

We Internet in the network Web pages let's see for WWW (World Wide web) that named from the service we use

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World Wide Web (WWW, Whole the world spider mesh) - this client-server technology based on established, wide is a distributed Internet service.

WWW (World Wide Web) is a certain place separated from the Internet no, not anything that the computer communicates with. The world spider net Internet within service to say more correct. Web servers that named by using certain protocols, computers (because they are connected to the network connected and server to the software have) Internet service on the way is placed.

Computer web server to be for to the Internet connected and server software is enough have supply. It's like Windows, Mac OS, Unix with DT operating systems can provide. A web server always "sits" on the Internet and Demand done towards necessary information will send

Hosting and domain concepts Steps to create a website Create a website methods

Web technology classification.

Razmetkali languages: HTML, XML, XHTML, WML.

Web technology (Internet technology) Web design part to learn fancy language classification with let's start

There is a special language, using this language texts , graphic data Web- the page is placed in the document and the ability to view this document on all computers is available. Such special languages coded languages that is called

Razmetkali languages

1. XHTML
2. XML
3. HTML
4. URL at applied protocols list:

Protocol name	Protocol why friend to give possible
http://	HTTP (web) to the servers
https://	• Encrypted SomeHTTP (web) to the servers
file://	User hard on the disk to files
ftp://	FTP server to files
gopher://	Gopher menu and to files
<u>news://</u>	Usenet news servers to the group
news:	Clearly Usenet news to the group
email:	Clearly electron mail to the address
telnet:	Telnet udalen to the server

Server on the side execution what cancer was ss e naries usually site folder inside special to the folder will be placed. User to the narrator basically server this ss e next performs Done ss e nary result to the web server is transmitted and from him so to the client is transmitted . Server on the side ss e narys organize reach for usually Perl , ASP , PHP , JSP and SSI such as language and from technologies is used .

1. Web programming technologies
2. server on the side programming
3. client-side programming

Summary

Today's in the day of our lives each one in the field Internet technologies we are using. Internet different different people single purpose with to merge is causing It is one of the important elements of Internet technologies web technologies too progressive reached is going now optional a person web of technologies a person of life education, commerce, politics, heart opens into pieces come in that he went imagination eat takes and his witness and becoming a user. Different programming languages based on the science of web programming using websites Create possible Har one programming of the language to himself hos has advantages and disadvantages. See their differences in this guide we passed A web page is a collection of files located on Internet networks, the number of which hour as increased is going This in the files information different types: text, graphic, image, video, audio data can be found. Web today It is the most popular among Internet resources. Because it is already prepared How much is the user's responsibility to fill in relevant information through the web page? how much the time savings enable gives That's it therefore mathematics and informatics as a separate course for students studying Web technologies is taught started

A deep desire to master this science is modern to be created in the future the level of information technologies will undoubtedly raise.

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